

Examining Medieval Long-Wall frontier systems (11th – 12th centuries AD) through archaeological geophysics in the Eastern Mongolian Steppe Region

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Medieval Wall System
Frontiers
Geophysics
Mongolia
Rammed Earth Wall Construction
Kitan/Liao Dynasty

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results of exploratory geophysical surveys and ground truthing of a cluster of earthen enclosures associated with a long-wall frontier system in northeastern Mongolia. This system dates to the 11th to early 12th centuries AD and was constructed by the Kitan/Liao Dynasty. Square and circular enclosures identified along the south side of the wall system were examined using single axis fluxgate gradiometry and ground penetrating radar. Geophysical prospection assisted in the identification of entry gates, rammed earth wall construction techniques, and interior features within the earthen complexes and assisted with the placement of ground truthing trenches. This approach ensured that geophysical survey was integrated closely with on-going development of the research design for the site and aided the identification and interpretation of construction characteristics associated with the long-wall system and the functions of the enclosures.

1. Introduction

Between the 10th and the early 13th centuries AD, a vast array of long-walls and border lines with associated *enclosures* were constructed in different regions of northern Eurasia. Today, these systems are located in the territories of north China and Mongolia with a small section in the east of Russia. Collectively, these constructions, which are often referred to as the Jin border trench (Chinese: *Jin Jiehao*), extend over an estimated length of 4,000 km (Storozum et al., 2021) (Fig. 1). Wall remains associated with the Jin dynasty are mentioned by Chinese travelers already in the 13th century CE and modern research was first spear-headed by the eminent Chinese historian Wang Guowey (1877–1927) (Wang 1921; for a more comprehensive survey of the history of the research see Shelach-Lavi et al., forthcoming).

Scholars are generally in agreement that the different wall lines were built sometime between the 10th to the 13th centuries AD. During this period, just prior to the rise of Chinggis Khan and the establishment of the Mongolian empire, non-Sinitic people including the Kitan, Tangut

and Jurchen, established dynasties in northern China and parts of Mongolia. While these dynasties were most likely responsible for the construction of different wall lines, the scarcity of relevant historic records has stimulated wide debate on the chronology and function of these large-scale landscape features (Baasan 2006; Danda'er 2013; Kradin 2019; Xie et al., 2020). We prefer to label the entire wall-building phenomenon as the 'Medieval Wall System' (MWS) and do not assume that it was an entirely preplanned system or even that it was built by a single dynasty (Fung et al. 2023; Shelach-Lavi et al. 2020a and 2020b; Storozum et al., 2021; and see also Danda'er 2013). Following Wang's pioneering research, many scholars believe that the MWS were built as military installations to stop invading armies (e.g. Chinggis Khan's Mongol armies or earlier invasions). However, based on the structure of the wall-lines, as well as analysis of the geographic positioning of the lines and the location of associated structures vis-à-vis the wall lines, we have argued that most of the lines were probably built to control and regulate the movement of people, including nomadic people and their herds (Shelach-Lavi et al., 2020a; 2020b; forthcoming).

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2024.104860>

Received 12 July 2024; Received in revised form 30 October 2024; Accepted 31 October 2024

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Archaeological research, to date, has been limited and this paper reports on new research that is part of a broader, systematic archaeological project examining these intriguing constructions. Funded by a grant from the European Research Council (ERC), The Wall Research Project integrates archaeological, historical, and environmental approaches to deepen our understanding of the Mongolian Wall System (MWS). Previous studies by Mongolian, Russian, and Chinese scholars

(e.g. Baasan 2006; Danda'er. 2013; Kradin 2019; Sun and Wang 2008; Xie et al., 2020), have focused on fragmented historical evidence and regional-scale mapping of the wall lines. Our research continues in this vein (Shelach-Lavi et al., forthcoming; Storozum et al., 2021), but also emphasizes a site-based approach, investigating clusters of enclosed features along the northern wall line. This has included the use of intensive pedestrian survey, archaeological geophysics and targeted

FIG. 1. A-B Location of the Medieval Wall System in Asia (Figure by Dan Golan); C – map of the Northern Wall line and a geographic cross-section of it showing the location of the clusters of enclosures located along its course.

excavations at several locations (Amartuvshin et al., 2024; Fung et al., 2023; Shelach-Lavi et al., 2020a and 2020b). This paper specifically explores Cluster 23, a previously identified area, to better understand its role in the broader context of the MWS.

Among the different sections of the MWS, one of the main targets of our research so far has been the 'Northern Line', which stretches 737 km across the grasslands of the border area between present day Mongolia, Russia, and China. Our survey has identified 42 clusters of enclosure features located along (and south of) the main wall/ditch line. Each of these clusters is made up of between 1–3 earthen walled enclosures of different sizes (Fig. 1, B) (Fung et al., 2023; Shelach-Lavi et al., 2020a

and 2020b). Contrary to the commonly held view that this wall-line was constructed by the Jin (Jurchen) dynasty (CE 1115–1234), radiocarbon dating of twelve samples recovered by our excavations at cluster no. 23 as well as in two other clusters along this line place its construction and use to the time of the Liao (Kitan) dynasty (AD 916–1125) (a list of C14 dates is provided in the supplementary materials). A relatively large number of flakes and flint tools found at this site, especially by our survey and excavations inside the large rectangular enclosure, suggest an earlier phase of human activity. While we did not find any architectural feature associated with this phase, and are unable to date it precisely, the nature of the artifacts suggests activity during the

Fig. 2. Google Earth satellite image of Cluster 23 with main archaeological features denoted.

Neolithic period (C. 5th-4th millennia BCE).

Since 2019, our team has conducted excavations at three of the 'Northern Line' clusters (23, 24 and 27). In this paper, we focus more specifically on detailing the integration of archaeological geophysics surveys associated with the excavations at Cluster 23, also known as Kheremtiyn (Kradin 2019: 129-130 and Figs 56-58), located at 49°05.42460' 115°10.16200'. We choose to focus on this site because it is relatively complex, includes three types of enclosures, and because these features are well preserved. Since our primary focus in the 2022 field season was the enclosures, we did not undertake geophysical survey over the wall line.

Cluster 23 consists of three main features: small and large square enclosures and a large circular enclosure (Fig. 2). The two square enclosures are located some 500 m south of the wall line. Their sizes are c. 30x30m and 60x60m, respectively, and their earthen walls currently stand approximately 2 m high. The circular enclosure is located some 750 m further to the south (1300 m south of the main wall line) and is 140 m in diameter. The wall of this enclosure is approximately 1 m high. In August 2022, our team excavated at six different locations around these three enclosures: a trench through the wall and ditch of the large square (Fig. 3, area E); two test pits outside (east of) the walls of the large square (Fig. 3, areas A and B); the gate area of the small square enclosure (Fig. 6, area D); a trench through the wall and ditch of the circular enclosure (Fig. 7, area C); and a test pit inside the circular enclosure (Fig. 7, area F). Our principal aim was to date the time of construction

and possible patterns of use of the three enclosures to better understand their function and relationship to the main wall system. Additional research at this site will focus on the analysis of eco-facts and artifacts that may contribute to a better understanding of the activities of the people who built and occupied these enclosures.

1.1. Integration of archaeological geophysics

Over the past twenty-five years, the field of archaeological geophysics has advanced rapidly, driven by technological innovations and the adoption of broader landscape perspectives that integrate these methods (Kvamme 2003). In recent years, scholars have emphasized that geophysics can play a more central role in shaping research design and excavation strategies, rather than merely serving as a tool to explore pre-determined research questions or archaeological features in isolation (Horsley et al. 2014: 76; Thompson et al. 2011: 196). Geophysical methods have proven to be efficient in many regions of the world, offering high-resolution imaging of archaeological features and complementing more conventional site-based survey approaches (Cuenca-García et al., 2024: viii). The 2022 field research at Cluster 23 sought to integrate a seven-day geophysical campaign during the initial phase of archaeological research at this site and was employed alongside drone based aerial imagery, pedestrian survey, soil augering, and test unit excavations. To our knowledge, no other geophysical surveys of the long-wall system have been undertaken or published and so the data

Fig. 3. A – drone image of large square with grey scale plot showing results of fluxgate gradiometry; B – fluxgate gradiometry plot detailing magnetic responses from interior and adjacent northern and western areas; C – topographic plan showing location of ground truthing excavations (A, B & E) (map by Or Fenigstein); D – interpretation plot of fluxgate gradiometry identifying key magnetic anomalies likely associated with archaeology (I – rammed earth wall feature; II – probable internal ditch feature; III – probable infilled pit and ditch features across surveyed area).

Fig. 4. A – the northern (right side) and southern (left side) sections of trench in area E cutting through external ditch feature of the large rectangular enclosure, identified in fluxgate gradiometry; B – excavation trench showing rammed earth wall feature (eastern face showing); C- photogrammetry image of the excavation profile showing rammed earth wall on left and ditch feature on right (photos and photogrammetry by Tal Rogovski).

presented in this paper represent the first use of these methods to explore these types of archaeological features in the region.

1.2. Site geology

Site 23 is situated within the northeastern part of the Ereendavaa terrane of the Kherlen massif, which represents the Mongolian part of the Argun-Idermeg superterrane (Kotov et al., 2013; Parfenov et al., 2009). This area also has been termed the Central Mongolia-Erguna Belt (Wang et al., 2017). The site is located at the western margin of Holocene silty sediments that are most likely of lacustrine origin. The site sits on a fault separating the Neoproterozoic Ereendavaa Terrane composed of metamorphic, sedimentary and volcanic rocks and Middle Gobi Volcano-Plutonic belt of the Permian Period composed of granites (Bussien et al., 2011). In the near vicinity of the site there are Mesozoic volcanic and sedimentary sequences that were intruded by Upper Paleozoic and Early Mesozoic Tsenkhergol, Ulzhol and Tsav granite and granodiorite complexes. Soil augering around the enclosed features revealed distinct soil horizons that were mainly variations of typical loess sediments. These included a dark brown, organic-rich horizon just below the turf level, a light brown, sandy horizon, an orange-brown sandy horizon, and a yellow natural soil layer generally occurring below 60 cm. More complex soil characteristics were associated with the enclosure features, as these were likely constructed using a rammed earth technique. This process produced substantial contrasts in the density and types of soils encountered and therefore were often visible

as stronger wave reflections with ground penetrating radar survey. In other instances, we encountered infilled trench and/or pit features that represented mixed soil contexts containing ash, faunal remains, and other artifacts. These infilled features were generally more magnetic than the immediate surrounding areas and were readily identifiable with magnetometry survey. Overall, due to the underlying geology of the site area, and characteristics of the sediment horizons noted above, magnetic and ground penetrating radar surveys were very effective in producing visible subsurface contrasts that aided subsequent ground truthing strategies.

2. Materials and methods

A strategy of multiple geophysical methods was employed as it has been shown that different methods will respond to different dimensions of surface and subsurface soil properties. This approach can assist with the identification and interpretation of geophysical responses and related archaeological features (Kvamme et al. 2006). In each zone chosen for geophysical survey, we first surveyed with a single axis fluxgate gradiometry because of its speed and ability to offer subsurface magnetic characterization and potential relationships to anthropogenic features. Gradiometry was followed with more spatially limited (due to time constraints) ground penetrating radar, multi-depth electromagnetic conductivity, and surface magnetic susceptibility. Pedestrian survey and soil augering also contributed to decision making regarding placement of ground truthing units. Spatial control of geophysical data

Fig. 5. A – Grey scale plot of fluxgate gradiometry survey over east wall of small square enclosure (20 m x 20 m survey block); B – fluxgate gradiometry plot showing key magnetic responses and clipped data range (C – ground penetrating radar slice view (55–60 cm below surface) showing strong radar reflections from rammed earth wall feature (yellow line denotes traverse line 4, detailed in image E) and multiple round reflections in the center of the gate area that correspond to the post features identified during excavation (1); D – interpretation of magnetic responses from gradiometry (I – rammed earth wall; II – probable infilled ditch feature; III – areas of high negative and positive magnetic responses from historic metal debris); E – radar profile of traverse 4 showing strong multi-reflections from rammed earth wall. Profile has been topographically corrected for surface elevations.

Fig. 6. A – topographical plan of small square enclosure with location of excavation area (map by Or Fenigstein); B – drone image showing location of excavation area D; C – a view from west to east (from outside the enclosure to the inside) of the enclosure gate. The preservation of the walls as well as the construction layers of the rammed earth method are clearly visible; D – an orthophoto of excavation area D, showing the gate walls and location of timber posts (photos by Tal Rogovski).

was obtained through the use of 20 m x 20 m grid units set out using meter tapes and triangulation methods. All grid corner points were recorded with an RTK GPS (GeoGenie Pro and NX system) with sub meter accuracy. Topographic relief of the archaeological features also was recorded using RTK GPS and a drone was utilized for aerial imagery. In this paper, due to space constraints, we focus specifically on the results of the fluxgate gradiometry and GPR methods and their clear correlation with ground truthing results. A fuller discussion of the other geophysical methods will be presented in a separate paper.

2.1. Single axis fluxgate gradiometry

Magnetometry is a widely used method in geophysical prospection for archaeology (Aspinall et al. 2008; Dalan 2006; Gaffney & Gater 2003). A Bartington Grad 601–2 single axis fluxgate gradiometer was utilized for our surveys, which can detect minute variations (± 0.01 to 100 nT) in the earth's magnetic field due to archaeological and geophysical subsurface features. This instrument has proven effective in the identification of infilled pits and ditches and burnt features such as hearths, kilns and ovens. Parallel transects were walked with this instrument in a zig-zag fashion using rope lines and/or fiberglass rods for path alignment. Measurements were taken with parallel traverse lines spaced every 1.0 m, or 0.5 m, with 8 data points collected each meter (0.125 m intervals). Data were downloaded and processed with

TerraSurveyor software. Processing steps included de-striping, edge-matching, de-staggering and clipping to approximately ± 1 STDV. Results were plotted and then traced for visualization with Adobe Illustrator for comparison and overlay with other geophysical data.

2.2. Ground penetrating radar (GPR)

GPR has been used successfully in archaeological and forensic field research since the early 1970 s and on a wide variety of prehistoric and historic sites (Conyers & Goodman 1997; Conyers 2013). GPR is an active method that is typically employed using parallel survey traverses within a grid either starting all traverses from the same grid edge or using a zig-zag pattern. GPR antennas transmit electromagnetic pulses into the ground as the instrument is pushed along the traverse and then measures the time from when these pulses are emitted until they are reflected back to the unit receivers. Individual wave reflections (wave-forms) of subsurface objects and features are plotted and digitized into two-dimensional reflection traces that produce profile/line views of the transects and depths and amplitude of the reflections. These data can be further processed to produce amplitude depth slices that yield plan views of the areas surveyed and anomalies associated with specific depths from the ground surface level. GPR data processed in these two ways have the potential to provide both spatial location and characterization of subsurface anomalies. A Sensors and Software Nogging

Fig. 7. A – satellite image of the circular enclosure with overlay of fluxgate gradiometer survey over northern half; B – fluxgate gradiometry plot detailing magnetic responses from northern half of circular enclosure; C – topographical plan with location of excavation areas C and F; D – interpretation plot of fluxgate gradiometry identifying key magnetic anomalies likely associated with archaeology (I – infilled pit/trench features; II – ditch features associated with perimeter fortification; III – rammed earth wall feature; IV – compacted soil and/or areas where magnetic topsoil has been removed; V – magnetically enhanced areas possibly related to rammed wall construction and/or erosion of wall feature; VI – area of complex dipolar anomalies possibly related to anthropogenic activities; VII – complex dipolar responses likely associated with a modern dirt trackway (a) and historic metal debris (b)).

SmartCart system was used with a 500 MHz antenna. Rope lines were utilized within grid squares at either 0.5 m or 1.0 m traverse spacing depending on specific objectives of the survey and probable size of potential anomalies. Data were downloaded to a laptop computer and processed with Sensors and Software's Ekko Project v6.0, a dedicated processing software for ground penetrating radar. Topographical correction, utilizing RTK GPS elevation data, also was used for traverses running perpendicular to wall and ditch features at the site.

2.3. Soil augering and excavation

Soil augering was employed systematically within the large circular enclosure. A total of 29 randomly selected locations were sampled within the enclosed space. In each location that we augered, we looked for anthropogenic remains, which unfortunately were not identified, and soil samples were taken for further FTIR analysis. In addition, we augered at locations within and near the two square enclosures where geophysical results suggested the possible existence of subsurface anthropogenic features, to help place test unit excavations, and for wider soil sampling across the site. We utilized a hand operated instrument 8.2 cm in diameter and augered in spits of 10 cm with each spit placed on a canvas for soil characterization and sample collection for subsequent FTIR and phytolith analysis. Auger holes generally extended 1–1.5 m in depth to the sterile soil horizon.

Test unit excavations did not aim to expose large areas but rather to address specific research questions regarding the nature of the enclosures and evidence of activities in the exterior and interior zones. The rate of sedimentation at the site is low and most anthropogenic features were found close to the surface. The size of the excavation units depended on the specific feature. For example, long narrow trenches were placed through the walls and ditches of the circular and square enclosures. When interesting features were encountered, such as the gate at the small rectangular enclosure, we expanded the test unit area. Our excavations took note of the natural and anthropogenic strata but when no such strata were observed we excavated in 10 cm spits to allow for stratigraphic control. The location of all features, samples, and important artifacts were recorded using RTK GPS and we produced orthophoto documentation of every phase of the excavations. Soil samples were taken flotation and chemical analysis. All excavated soils were dry sieved to recover small artifacts, bones and other materials. These results will be reported in a future publication.

3. Results and discussion

Initial results of geophysical surveys were available during field research on a day-to-day basis and contributed to the strategies outlined above for soil augering and test unit excavations. In this paper, we focus specifically on results obtained at the large and small enclosure features

and the circular enclosure.

3.1. Geophysical survey results of the large square feature

Fluxgate gradiometry survey was employed within the interior area of the large square feature and to the north and east of the walls (Fig. 3). A total of twenty 20 m x 20 m grid squares were utilized (0.8 ha). Survey was undertaken with 1 m spacing of instrument probes in a zig zag collection pattern with a north-south orientation. Data collection for the four grids placed over the eastern wall of the feature were completed in an east-west orientation to ensure a perpendicular axis to the wall and subsurface ditch features. Gradiometry results identified numerous positive magnetic anomalies that are likely infilled pit or ditch "type" features, including what appears to be an internal ditch feature that parallels the rammed earth wall (Fig. 3, B-D). The larger positive anomalies ranged from approximately +1nT to +30nT (4-8 m in diameter) and the probable internal ditch anomaly ranged from +1nT to +15nT. Several strong small dipoles were identified (<1m diameter), however, these appeared to be associated with surface metal debris (likely modern). No strong, discrete dipolar anomalies were identified that would be expected for high temperature kiln or furnace archaeological features. Surprisingly, the positive pit and/or trench anomalies identified within the interior of the square did not appear to align with the expected spatial orientation of the square walls, however, these were not ground truthed during the 2022 season and will be examined in the future. Three excavation units were placed within the eastern zone of the feature (Fig. 3, C-D). The unit in Area E did bisect an identified positive magnetic anomaly, which was initially interpreted as a possible ditch feature in the fluxgate gradiometry results.

3.1.1. Ground truthing results of areas A, B and E

To test the results of the geophysical survey and better understand the composition of the wall of the large square enclosure we excavated an elongated 15 m x 2 m wide trench that cut through the east wall and extended to the east (Figs. 3 and 4). The trench exposed a rammed earth wall that is 2.2 m wide and is preserved to a height of 81 cm. The base of the wall is more than half a meter higher than the level of the surrounding ground, suggesting that the rammed-earth wall was built on top of an artificial mound, made of brown soil (paleosol). The relatively wide negative anomaly seen in the gradiometry results represents the outline of this foundation mound while the stronger negative anomalies may be associated with the rammed earth wall, which is made of light-colored chalky material. The outline of this wall is clearly seen in the results of the geophysical survey (Fig. 3, A-B). East of it we identified the remains of an enclosing ditch that was infilled with soil layers that accumulated after the enclosure was abandoned. Artifacts also were recovered in this area that likely relate to contemporaneous occupation activities. Not including the later accumulation of soil, the ditch feature was approximately 1.8 m in depth. Our excavations indicate that the orientation of the ditch in this location was not parallel to the large square enclosure's wall but was rather oblique and ran in a general SW-NE direction. The "turn" of the ditch is clearly visible in the results of the geophysical survey (Fig. 3, B and D).

Following the initial gradiometry results, we augered at a few locations east of the enclosure's ditch and then placed test units in two locations (Fig. 3, C, Areas A and B) where augering produced ashy soil and faunal remains. Archaeological features encountered in the Area A and B test units turned out to be midden deposits containing approximately a 1 m depth accumulation of ashy soil, faunal remains, and discarded artifacts. While their locations do not correspond precisely to the strongest positive anomalies detected, they are closely associated spatially.

3.1.2. Geophysical survey results of the small square feature

Fluxgate gradiometry surveys were employed over the interior and eastern wall of the small square (Fig. 2). The interior area contained a

significant amount of historical metal debris and an effort was made to remove objects visible on the surface. However, following survey, the data indicated that there also were metal objects present below the surface and this adversely affected the gradiometry results over the interior area of the small square. An additional grid (400 m²), for both fluxgate gradiometry and GPR, was placed over the eastern wall of the feature where the modern debris created less magnetic disturbance (Fig. 5). The topographical relief of the wall is lower in this area and it was thought that an entrance gate may have been positioned here. The results of both fluxgate gradiometry and GPR surveys supported this expectation (Fig. 5, A-C). Gradiometry survey produced positive responses over the wall feature, ranging from approximately +3nT to +15nT. A clear break in this anomaly is visible in Fig. 5 (A, B & D) correlating with the topography. The positive magnetic response is likely associated with soils used in the wall construction that may have been more magnetically susceptible, which, it should be noted, differed from the negative magnetic responses over the wall in the large square feature (discussed above). GPR survey over the small square wall produced strong reflections resulting from the rammed earth construction and are visible in both a slice view and topographically corrected traverse line (Fig. 5, C & E). The slice view also indicates a break in the wall line where a gate was suspected and three small circular shaped reflections were identified in this area as well, which were initially interpreted as possibly associated with a gate system (Fig. 5, C-1). Following the geophysical survey, a ground truthing excavation unit (Area D) was placed within this area to substantiate the geophysical interpretations and topographical relief (Fig. 6).

3.1.3. Ground truthing results of area D

Excavations of the gate area on the eastern wall of the small enclosure confirmed our surface observations and the results of the geophysical survey (Fig. 6). Our excavations revealed the remains of a highly compact rammed earth wall and a well-structured gate opening in this wall. The wall in this location is 4.4 m wide and is preserved to a height of 50 cm. The width of the gate feature is 2 m. Twelve large wooden poles were well preserved and formed a part of the gate structure. These were placed in two rows of four on each side of the gate and pairs of poles inside the gate marked the entrance and exit of the gate (Fig. 6, D). The small circular reflections noted above in the GPR slice view, appear to correlate with the pole features encountered during excavation (Fig. 5, C-1; Fig. 6, B, D), however, these are not detectable in the fluxgate gradiometry survey (Fig. 5, A-B).

3.1.4. Geophysical survey results of the circular enclosure

Geophysical surveys were conducted in the circular enclosure and focused on a fluxgate gradiometry survey of the northern half (1.64 ha) and on a smaller (300 m²) focused GPR survey over the ditch and bank area in the western zone of the site (Fig. 2; Fig. 7). The gradiometer survey utilized one meter probe spacing, which was chosen to survey as large an area as possible given the time available (2 days). Smaller diameter features (<1 m), such as post molds, were likely not systematically identifiable with this traverse spacing. Nevertheless, several positive magnetic responses do appear to indicate possible foundation lines, pit features, or small hearths (+1nT to +10nT). Additional gradiometry survey utilizing narrower traverse spacing and ground truthing will be needed to investigate these potential features. Several complex dipolar anomalies, possibly related to burning and/or thermal features such as kilns or furnaces, were also identified in the data (Fig. 7, D, V). The gradiometry also responded clearly to the ditch and bank features associated with the perimeter of the site and indicated curvilinear positive anomalies (probable infilled depression features) and parallel negative features (rammed earth wall and areas where more magnetically susceptible soils may have been removed during the construction) (Fig. 7, B & D). These results correlate well with the topographical relief of the circle and represent a highly active zone of construction for the circular feature (Fig. 7, C).

A modern dirt track runs north–south across the site and this affected the gradiometry results (Fig. 7, A & D). Additional strong, complex dipolar anomalies likely represent modern activity and/or metal debris. Numerous positive monopolar anomalies were identified within the enclosed area of the circle and ranged from + 1nT to + 5nT. These likely represent pits and other subsurface features infilled with more magnetically susceptible soils. One of these anomalies, curvilinear in nature and ranging from + 2nT to + 5nT, was explored through a 2 m x 2 m test unit (Area F) and was confirmed to be a small ditch feature (Fig. 8). The ground truthing results of this are discussed in more detail below. An additional large linear positive anomaly was identified immediately to the west of the far western periphery of the circle and may relate to a construction feature associated with the circular enclosure.

A GPR survey grid (300 m²) was positioned ten meters to the north of the excavation area C. Both the excavation trench and GPR survey were placed to incorporate the western ditch and bank area of the circle perimeter (Fig. 7, C; Fig. 9). As the excavation began prior to the geophysical survey it was not possible to survey over the excavated area. GPR survey collected data with 0.5 m traverse spacing and provided strong responses over the external ditch and to some degree the rammed earth wall feature, which was topographically corrected for the variation in elevation (Fig. 9, C-D). There were a number of additional GPR responses in the eastern area of the survey (probable compacted surfaces) that appear to correspond to magnetic (positive and negative) anomalies also identified in the fluxgate gradiometer survey. Additional ground truthing would be needed to explore these responses. The excavation of Area C provided important information on the materials and structure of the ditch and bank construction and these conform well with the geophysical responses achieved through gradiometry and GPR.

3.1.5. Ground truthing results of the circular enclosure (Areas C and F)

Area F effectively illustrates the integration of geophysical survey as

a guide for excavation. There were no indications on the surface for the existence of anything below the ground and auguring in this area of the circular enclosure did not produce any significant results that would suggest otherwise. However, the fluxgate geophysical surveys identified here a long curvilinear anomaly. Auguring where we thought this anomaly should be placed on the ground recovered an ashy material some 50 cm below the surface as well as a fragment of animal bone. A small 2x2m excavation unit was placed around the auguring location (Fig. 8, A, Area F;). At a depth of 40 cm below the surface a wide line of darker softer soil appeared at the center of the unit (Fig. 8, C). The feature identified here was a ditch 75 cm wide and 50 cm deep (the bottom was 90 cm below surface) and running in a northeast – southwest direction (Fig. 8, D). A few potshards and animal bones were found near the bottom of the ditch, one of them relatively complete (Fig. 8, B). Analysis of two charcoal samples from the bottom of this ditch produced radiocarbon dates that are contemporaneous with dates from other areas of the site and the dates recovered from other clusters along the wall line (see [supplementary materials](#)).

Our trench through the wall and ditch of the circular enclosure (Fig. 7, Area C) produced results that are similar to what we see in the large rectangular enclosure (Fig. 3, Area E). The enclosure had a rammed earth wall (Fig. 10) that is 160 cm wide with a preserved height of 65 cm. It was built on top of an artificial mound, made of piled brown soil (paleosol). External to the wall there was a ditch that is 4 m wide at the top and 2 m at the bottom with a depth of 1.7 m (Fig. 10, A). Within the ditch are layers of soil, including ashy soil horizons, which accumulated during the time of occupation but most likely after the site was abandoned. While the general outline of the wall and ditch confirm the results of the geophysical survey, in our excavation that extended beyond the wall line and into the interior of the circular enclosure, we did not find clear evidence for an internal ditch, which initially seemed to be indicated by the fluxgate gradiometry results. This positive response from gradiometry, which clearly parallels the negative

Fig. 8. A – fluxgate gradiometry plot of area where excavation Unit F was placed; B – potshards recovered from bottom of ditch in Unit F; C – dark stain of ditch feature visible in photo of Unit F; D – photo showing profile of ditch feature (photos by Tal Rogovski).

Fig. 9. A – fluxgate gradiometry plot of area north of excavation area C (yellow rectangle represents area surveyed with GPR); B – ground penetrating radar slice view (30–35 cm below surface) showing radar reflections from ditch and features (yellow line denotes traverse line 7, detailed in image D); C – sketch plan of ditch and bank topographic features; D – radar profile of traverse line 7 showing reflections from external ditch, rammed earth wall, and probable compacted surfaces in the interior. GPR profile has been topographically corrected for surface elevation.

response from the rammed earth wall, and the positive response from the external infilled ditch, may be related to the construction of the fortification and the preparation of a foundation (mounded brown paleosol) for the rammed earth wall (Fig. 10, A-B). This brown layer of soil may have been taken from the upper soil horizon during construction and such soils are typically more magnetically enhanced due to natural and cultural activity (Dalan 2006). Because this foundation extended beyond the parameters of the rammed earth wall and into the

interior of the enclosure it was identified here as a positive response with gradiometry. We also noted that both the fluxgate magnetic responses and GPR reflections were different over the eastern wall of the small square and the western wall and ditch of the circle. This fact would indicate that the nature of construction, and possibly soils used, were different. For example, during the excavation in Area D at the small enclosed square, small stones were identified within the rammed earth wall. Stone material was not identified in the Area C unit placed in the

Fig. 10. A – photogrammetry image showing the profile of area C trench through the wall of the circular enclosure (central part of the picture) and the ditch outside of it (left side); B – a view from inside the circular enclosure of the light colored strata of the rammed earth wall built on top of brown-colored soil (view to the west); C – a view from outside the circular enclosure of the light colored strata of the rammed earth wall built on top of brown-colored soil. The piling of the brown-colored soil can be seen in the sections on both sides of the excavation trench (photos and photogrammetry by Tal Rogovski).

circle perimeter.

4. Conclusions

The implementation of geophysical survey, in conjunction with pedestrian survey, soil augering, and stratigraphic excavations at Cluster 23, indicates the productive nature of conducting these activities simultaneously. Geophysical survey provided subsurface data in real time and helped to inform the strategic placement of subsurface testing. In this way, both sets of activities informed each other during the course of field research. The fluxgate gradiometry surveys provided a rapid, first step approach that guided more detailed geophysical survey, such as GPR, as well as soil augering and placement of excavation areas. GPR survey provided an important complementary dataset to gradiometry as it provided a potential understanding of subsurface stratigraphic relationships (Conyers 2018). The ground truthing results discussed in this paper support this. In conclusion, a high degree of geophysical coverage of three separate site features (Fig. 2) was possible within a single week of field research and indicated that multi-method geophysical surveys offer a highly beneficial approach to the study of long-wall systems. These results encourage the integration of geophysical survey in future studies and more detailed analysis of the construction characteristics of associated enclosed earthen structures and associated features.

The use of geophysical methods enabled us, in the time constraints of our field work, to better achieve our goal of understanding the MWS from a smaller scale perspective. The research also contributes importantly to a site-focused approach to understanding what has been long perceived as an extensive frontier system. Our studies have identified important archaeological features that provide more information on the lifeways of the populations who occupied the enclosed cluster sites. For

example, through the identification of anomalies located outside the large rectangular enclosure, we were able to identify and excavate midden deposits that were not visible on the surface through pedestrian survey. Our excavation of these features provided evidence for sedentism, yielding substantial quantities of animal bones and broken artifacts. Such an extensive amount of midden material is not usually found during archaeological excavations of pastoral nomadic camps, suggesting then, that the human occupation of Cluster 23 was more extensive and of a longer duration. Identification of the different animal species recovered from the midden deposits provides an important indication of the subsistence practices of the people occupying the site. As might be expected, the majority of faunal remains represent sheep and goat, reflecting a common local economy for populations inhabiting the steppe region. The horse remains recovered may be associated with the military function of the site. Other recovered species, including bones of gazelle and large catfish, index a subsistence economy that drew on available resources from the wider region and suggest that the inhabitants were not solely dependent on domestic livestock.

Based on the combined results of our geophysical survey and stratigraphic excavations, we estimate that the two rectangular enclosures were intensively occupied. The elaborate gate feature we excavated at the smaller rectangular enclosure, along with the larger walls of the feature, suggests that it may have held greater symbolic importance, possibly serving as a locus of authority. The larger rectangular enclosure was likely associated with more mundane activities, such as housing the people who occupied the site and defended the adjacent wall line. The purpose of the circular enclosure remains unclear. While our initial hypothesis suggested it functioned as an animal corral, the significant investment required to construct the surrounding wall and ditch challenges this interpretation. Additionally, soil samples taken from the

augering probes in the circular enclosure did not reveal chemical traces typically associated with extensive animal use. Many questions remain to be answered regarding the construction and use of the enclosure cluster that formed an important component of the northern wall line, however, through the use of multiple methods, including geophysics, soil chemistry, and targeted excavations, we are beginning to gain a deeper understanding of these intriguing constructions and the people who constructed them and occupied the frontier zones of northern Eurasia.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Bryan K. Hanks: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Gideon Shelach-Lavi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marc Bermann:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Emily Eklund:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Aspen Greaves:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Chunag Amartuvshin:** . **Narantsetseg Tserendash:** Validation, Supervision, Investigation, Data curation. **Yonatan Goldsmith:** Validation, Resources, Investigation, Data curation. **Jargalan Burentogtokh:** Resources, Investigation, Data curation. **Ulbabayar Erdenebat:** .

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This research was supported by the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (“The Wall” project, grant agreement No. 882894) with additional support for the geophysical survey by the Dietrich School of Arts and Sciences, University of Pittsburgh.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2024.104860>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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